

AN ANALYSIS OF STUDIES RELATED TO NEW ASPECTS OF QUINONE CHEMISTRY

¹Meenakshi Nirman*

¹Associate Professor, Department of Chemistry, Government PG College Sec-1,
Panchkula, Haryana, India

Email ID: nirmanpragyan@gmail.com

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Abstract

The current invention involves the synthesis of naphthoquinone derivatives and many of their geometric/structural isomers by a unique approach utilising 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone, followed by characterisation. To improve yield and purity, a number of parameters have been changed in the new technique. Since acetonitrile, a costly and increasingly scarce solvent, is consumed in significant quantities during the aforementioned process, research has been done on its recovery and reuse from mother liquors. The recovery and repurposing of silver salt by converting it to silver nitrate was also covered in the study because silver nitrate is an expensive material that significantly affects overall costs. Since we have learnt for the first time the properties of silver salt, its conversion to silver nitrate, and its subsequent reutilization in the reaction, the result of silver from the aforementioned reaction is not yet documented in the literature. By replacing weak hydrochloric acid with acetic acid during the separation of Atovaquone (8) from the reaction mass, polar contaminants were removed, improving purity. Through the use of a solvent combination, the current study sought to produce Atovaquone form I with a minimum purity of 99%. According to the literature, a significant amount of acetonitrile is used in the recrystallisation of atovaquone to obtain form I. There is a lack of

commercial viability and a production bottleneck due to the extensive use of solvents. Unexpectedly, we have found that form I can be produced by a very small number of solvent combinations, and this could significantly increase the reactor's output. The recently synthesised compounds were tested for their anticancer and antimalarial qualities. A number of chemicals have shown a great deal of activity. By synthesising naphthoquinone derivatives from 2,3-dihalo naphthoquinone compounds, the current method partially or completely addresses all objectives. These derivatives can then be used to create 2-cyclohexyl-1,4-naphthoquinone derivatives, such as Atovaquone, Parvaquone, and tert-butyl Atovaquone. The aforementioned products can now be produced using an economically feasible, environmentally responsible, and industrially viable method.

Paper Identification

*Corresponding Author

Introduction

Quinones are organic substances that are officially descended from aromatic substances like naphthalene or

benzene. To obtain a completely conjugated cyclic dione structure¹, an even number of (CH) groups undergo oxidation to become (C=O) groups, and the required double bonds are rearranged. In addition, organic compounds with electron-donating substituents, including catechols and phenols, readily undergo oxidation to quinones. The ring's nucleophilicity is increased by the electron-donating substituents, which also help to provide the high redox potential required to break the aromaticity (quinones are conjugated but not aromatic). Quinone derivatives are used in a wide variety of natural and synthetic colouring agents, such as dyes and pigments. In terms of significance as dyestuffs with a focus on blue hues, they rank second only to azo dyes. Alizarin {1,2-dihydroxy-9,10-anthraquinone} (8) was the first natural dye made from anthracene, and it was taken from the madder plant. This was the most common red dye used to colour textiles.

Quinones, whether synthetic or natural, exhibit pharmacological or biological properties such as antitumoural, anticonvulsant, and antimicrobial properties. The literature information on the structure-activity-relationships of quinones are many and it is evident from innumerable reviews, research articles and books¹¹⁻¹³. In this chapter an attempt has been made to review the synthesis and biological activity of 1,4-naphthoquinones.

1,4-naphthoquinones

Naphthalene (9), an organic molecule, is the source of 1,4-naphthoquinone (3). It is a planar molecule that has a quinone subunit¹⁴ attached to one aromatic ring. It is made by aerobically oxidising naphthalene with either chromium trioxide¹⁶ or catalytic vanadium oxide¹⁵.

Scheme 2: Synthesis of 1,4-naphthoquinone (3)

Naphthoquinone forms the central chemical structure of numerous natural products, such as Vitamin K series (2-methyl-3-substituted-1,4-naphthoquinones), Juglone (10), Plumbagin (11) etc.

The manufacture, characterisation, and biological activity of atovaquone (24) against protozoal diseases brought on by microsporidia were described by Winston, E. G. et al. (32). In the presence of ammonium persulfate and silver nitrate, 2-chloro-1,4-naphthoquinone (23) was synthesised utilising a free radical approach. A powerful antimalarial³³, atovaquone (24) is a hydroxyl-1,4-naphthoquinone that exhibits high efficacy against leishmaniasis³⁵ and *Pneumocystis carinii*³⁴. Atovaquone's synthesis and anticancer efficacy were reported by Hudson et al. (36). Using a free radical reaction, 2-chloro-1,4-naphthoquinone (23) was used for synthesis.

The goal of this investigation

The biological significance of quinones prompted us to study some new aspects of quinone chemistry with special reference to Atovaquone (24) and its derivatives. Synthesis of Atovaquone (24) involves the use of 2-

chloro-1,4-naphthoquinone (23), which is expensive and is not available readily. We planned to use 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone (25) instead of 2-chloro-1,4-naphthoquinone (23) and study the chemistry of this reaction. We also planned to study crystal structures of Atovaquone (24) and its derivatives based on conformational features. Docking studies have been planned for these compounds in order to have valuable insights into the atomistic details of protein-inhibitor interactions.

Atovaquone (24) is poorly soluble in most of the solvents and hence it has poor bioavailability. It is required to be used in higher dosages. To overcome this aspect we planned to make pro-drugs of Atovaquone which can generate Atovaquone (24) in-situ in the body. We also explored the synthesis of amino derivatives of naphthoquinone and studied their antimalarial and anticancer activities.

General procedure for the synthesis (4f-4i)

2-[trans-4-(4-chlorophenyl) cyclohexyl] 2-Chloro-3-[1.0 equivalent of 1,4-naphthoquinone, 1.5 equivalent of potassium carbonate powder, and 2.5 equivalent of substituted amines [benzylamine for (4f), hexamethyleneimine for (4g), phenylpiperazine for (4h), and 4-chloro phenylpiperazine for (4i)] and 10 volts of acetonitrile were heated to reflux for 10 to 96 hours. TLC tracked the completion of the reaction. filtered the bulk to get rid of the inorganic salts after cooling it to between 25 and 300 degrees Celsius. To get the crude residue, the solvent was entirely distilled off the filtrate under vacuum. After adding 5 volts of methanol to the residue, it was heated for 15 minutes to 45 to 500 degrees Celsius. To separate the product, the

heated reaction mass was filtered. The sample was vacuum-dried for one hour at 500C.

Conclusion

The quinone nucleus is incorporated in many drugs. Quinone derivatives find their applications as antifungal, antiprotozoal and anticancer medications. They also show various activities like antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antimalarial, anticoagulant, antiviral, anti-tubercular, anticancer etc. Quinones are also used in dye industry. Many compounds of industrial and technological importance contain quinone derivatives. The proper modulation of structures by modifications in the substituents on the basic quinone nucleus can lead to variations in the activity. Two carbonyl groups that may take one or two electrons to generate the matching radical anion or di-anion species are the primary source of quinones' biological activity. As a result, quinone has superior pharmacodynamic properties and is essential for cell metabolism as an electron transporter. Therefore, because of their biological relevance, substituted 1,4-naphthoquinones receive particular study.

Few novel derivatives of 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone and 2-Chloro-3-[trans-4-(4-chlorophenyl) cyclohexyl]-1,4-naphthoquinone were synthesized and characterized. In case of 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone derivatives synthesis required milder reaction conditions where as drastic reaction conditions were required for the synthesis of 2-Chloro-3-[trans-4-(4-chlorophenyl) cyclohexyl]-1,4-naphthoquinone. This behaviour can be attributed to steric hindrance in later case. All newly synthesized compounds were screened for antimalarial and anticancer activities. Among these compounds few of them found to be biologically active.

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